

Application of glycerol for induced powdery mildew resistance in *Triticum aestivum* L.

Glycerol-Induced Powdery Mildew Resistance in Wheat by Regulating Plant Fatty Acid Metabolism, Plant Hormones Cross-Talk, and Pathogenesis-Related Genes.

Application of glycerol as a foliar spray activates the defence response and enhances disease resistance of *Theobroma cacao*.

An oleic acid-mediated pathway induces constitutive defense signaling and enhanced resistance to multiple pathogens in soybean.

Glycerol-3-phosphate is a critical mobile inducer of systemic immunity in plants.

Glycerol-3-Phosphate Levels Are Associated with Basal Resistance to the Hemibiotrophic Fungus *Colletotrichum higginsianum* in *Arabidopsis*.

The common metabolite glycerol-3-phosphate is a novel regulator of plant defense signaling.

Oleic Acid–Dependent Modulation of NITRIC OXIDE ASSOCIATED1 Protein Levels Regulates Nitric Oxide–Mediated Defense Signaling in *Arabidopsis*.

Suppression of the rice fatty-acid desaturase gene *osssi2* enhances resistance to blast and leaf blight diseases in rice.

Transcriptional regulation of glycerol-3-phosphate metabolism Induces resistance to coffee rust.